

Research Article

Meal planning under uncertainty: How shopping frequency affects food waste

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ABSTRACT

Food waste is the undesired result of multiple household food management routines. To reduce this food waste, interventions typically promote either food waste prevention or food waste recovery behaviours. These behaviours can be contradictory when it comes to shopping practices. Food waste prevention strategies suggest shopping for multiple days at once to benefit from planning and coordinate food packages with the needs of several days, whereas food waste recovery advocates for more frequent shopping trips to account for the unpredictability of everyday life. This study isolates the impact of shopping frequencies on food waste, assessing its effects across varying levels of uncertainties related to who will be present for dinner. A mathematical meal planning model is formulated to generate dinner meal plans and shopping lists by selecting combinations of recipes while considering nutritional adequacy and package sizes. The model uses a rolling horizon approach to simulate meal planning for household situations that are facing varying uncertainties in ingredient needs. As a base case, the model is run over a 21-day horizon for a household of four persons. The analysis reveals a trade-off between the flexibility of frequent shopping and the benefits of coordinating food purchases. Households with higher uncertainty in food requirements benefit from more frequent shopping compared to those with more stable needs, with total food waste across shopping frequencies ranging from 0–52 grams, 46–300 grams, and 50–900 grams per 21-day horizon for low-, medium-, and high-uncertainty household profiles, respectively. Moreover, the findings show that food waste can be minimized to 3 grams per day across all uncertainty levels by selecting recipes based on the food items already in stock at home. These insights suggest that tailored shopping and meal planning strategies based on household uncertainty levels can substantially reduce food waste and inform targeted interventions.

1. Introduction

One-third of global food production is wasted (Gustavsson et al., 2011), which has severe adverse environmental, social, and economic effects. Environmentally, food waste indirectly leads to soil erosion, deforestation, water and air pollution, and significant greenhouse gas emissions (GHGE) (Schanes et al., 2018; FAO, 2013). From a social perspective, managing the food supply efficiently is crucial for feeding the growing world population (Foley et al., 2011). Economically, food waste results in substantial financial losses, with estimates suggesting billions of dollars wasted each year (FAO, 2013). Most food waste in the EU occurs at the household level, with an estimated wastage of 98.6 kilograms per person per year (Caldeira et al., 2019; Stenmarck et al., 2016). Therefore, the need to reduce food waste at the household level is evident.

Interventions targeting household food waste have predominantly focused on providing information (Reynolds et al., 2019; Stöckli et al.,

2018). The primary goal of these information interventions is to raise awareness of the negative consequences of food waste and set the intention to reduce waste. However, just providing information may not be sufficient. Studies show that there is an “intention-behaviour gap” regarding food waste (Stancu et al., 2016; Stöckli et al., 2018; Swannell et al., 2023), meaning that the intention to reduce food waste is not a good predictor for actual food waste reducing behaviour. On the other hand, interventions targeting household food management routines have proven more effective (Swannell et al., 2023; Stefan et al., 2013; Liechti et al., 2024). These can be categorized into food waste prevention and recovery behaviours (Cooper et al., 2023). Prevention behaviours, such as planning, aim to avoid a surplus of food reaching the household. Recovery behaviours, such as prioritizing the use of foods that are at risk of being thrown away, focus on using all the food that has entered the household. Although prevention behaviours have gained more attention in literature, Cooper et al. (2023) have recently stressed the importance of recovery behaviours.

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Nomenclature**Sets and indices**

$d \in \mathcal{D}$	Days
$f \in \mathcal{F}$	Days in stock, where $F = \max(\mathcal{F})$ is the shelf life
$i \in \mathcal{I}$	Ingredients
$i \in \mathcal{S}$	Shelf-stable ingredients
$j \in \mathcal{JD}$	Daily nutrients (water soluble)
$j \in \mathcal{JW}$	Weekly nutrients (fat soluble)
$p \in \mathcal{P}_i$	Package option (# of options vary per ingredient i , each option has a package size and package price)
$r \in \mathcal{R}$	Recipes

Decision variables

$BUY_{i,p}$	Integer. Number of packages of option p to buy of ingredient i .
$COST$	Continuous. Cost in euros of the meal plan in the forecast horizon.
$GHGE$	Continuous. Grams of CO ₂ equivalent emissions of the meal plan in the forecast horizon.
$NI_{j,d}$	Continuous. Nutrient intake of nutrient j on day d .
$REQ_{i,d}$	Continuous. Grams of ingredient i needed on day d (according to the recipe).
$STOCK_{i,d,f}$	Continuous. Stock of ingredient i on day d that has been purchased f days ago (grams).
$WASTE_{i,d}$	Continuous. Grams of ingredient i wasted on day d .
$X_{i,d}$	Continuous. Grams of ingredient i planned for day d .
$Y_{r,d}$	Binary. Whether recipe r is planned on day d (1) or not (0).
$Z_{i,d}$	Binary. Whether ingredient i is planned on day d (1) or not (0).

Parameters

$beginstock_{i,f}$	Stock of food item i purchased f days before the forecast horizon.
$days$	Number of days left in forecast horizon for which to formulate a planning.
$druRDA_j$	Dietary reference value RDA for nutrient j .
$druUL_j$	Dietary reference value UL for nutrient j .
$eaten_r$	Recipes r selected in the days prior to the forecast horizon.
$fc_{i,j}$	Food Composition Database. Amount of nutrient j in 100 grams of ingredient i (g, mg or μ g).
lca_{c_i}	Carbon footprint in kg for ingredient i in kg.
$packc_{i,p}$	Packing cost in euros per packing option p of ingredient i .
$packs_{i,p}$	Packing size in grams per packing option p of ingredient i .
$pers$	Number of persons for whom to formulate a planning.

$rec_{i,r}$	Ingredient i in grams needed per person for recipe r .
$shelFs_i$	Binary. Whether an ingredient i is shelf-stable (1) or not (0).

Food shopping practices focusing on food waste prevention or recovery behaviours can be contradictory. A prevention approach involves planning and shopping for multiple days, whereas a recovery approach suggests more frequent supermarket visits. Planning practices, such as making shopping lists and shopping for multiple meals in advance, can substantially reduce household food waste (Ananda et al., 2023; Stefan et al., 2013; Van Rooijen et al., 2024). However, effectively engaging in planning practices can be challenging due to the unpredictability of everyday life (Dobernig and Schanes, 2019; Evans, 2015; Ganglbauer et al., 2013). Unexpected guests turning up for dinner, or family members dining elsewhere may lead to a potential shortage or surplus of food in the household (Van Geffen et al., 2020; Evans, 2015). To address these uncertainties, some argue shopping more frequently could help households better adjust their food purchases to changing needs (Ellison et al., 2022).

Shopping frequency is a key factor in household food waste because it reflects the extent of meal planning. Typically, meals are planned, and shopping lists are created for a single shopping trip at a time, meaning the chosen planning horizon directly affects food purchasing. Shopping frequency also influences the selection of package sizes, which are among the main reported reasons for household food waste (Bo et al., 2022; Williams et al., 2012). According to Romani et al. (2018) meal planning and purchasing decisions have a significant impact on household food waste, as they occur at the very start of the food consumption process. Moreover, shopping frequency is a clearly measurable behaviour, making it an effective variable for studying waste reduction strategies.

There is no consensus in literature on a preferable shopping frequency to reduce food waste. The dynamic nature of everyday life has often been mentioned in relation to shopping frequency (Dobernig and Schanes, 2019; Evans, 2015; Ganglbauer et al., 2013; Ellison et al., 2022). To design effective interventions targeting food waste reduction, it is key to understand the theoretical interrelations of these elements (Reynolds et al., 2019; Stancu et al., 2016; Casonato et al., 2023). Thus, there is a need to study the relation between shopping frequency, uncertainty in food requirements, and food waste. Quantifying these effects is challenging due to many interrelating societal, individual, and behavioural factors affecting food waste (Boulet et al., 2021; Graham-Rowe et al., 2014; Nabi et al., 2021; Roodhuyzen et al., 2017; Schanes et al., 2018; Stangherlin and de Barcellos, 2018). Simulations of complex problems have proven helpful to isolate effects of individual factors (Glomb et al., 2022). However, those types of studies have not yet been used to study the effect of shopping frequency on food waste.

Mathematical diet modelling has proven to be an effective method for solving food planning problems (Gazan et al., 2018; Dooren, 2018). However, these diet models typically formulate a fixed plan for a set number of days and do not account for everyday unpredictability. In other domains, rolling horizon approaches have been applied to optimization problems that involve uncertainty (Chand et al., 2002). Building on this, this study develops a meal planning model following a rolling horizon approach. By combining these methods, the effects of shopping frequency and uncertainty in food requirements on food waste are isolated. This approach allows for the simulation of potential disruptions in meal planning that occur in everyday life. The model accounts for package sizes, costs, GHGE, and nutritional values. The results provide insights into shopping strategies for different family profiles, which can inform interventions and campaigns to reduce food waste. The Netherlands serves as a case study.

2. Literature review

Mathematical diet modelling applies optimization techniques to find the optimal combination of foods that most effectively meet specific objectives while adhering to constraints (Buttriss et al., 2014). Stigler (1945) was the first to formulate the so-called “diet problem”, aiming to find a set of foods that meet nutritional guidelines at the lowest cost. Over time, diet models have been extended to design nutritionally adequate, affordable, and/or environmentally friendly diets (see van Dooren (2018) and Gazan et al. (2018) for comprehensive reviews).

Traditional diet models focus on individual ingredients, which can make it difficult to translate these combinations into practical meals (Macdiarmid et al., 2012). For example, a model might suggest ingredients that meet nutritional targets but do not work together as a culturally acceptable meal. In contrast, meal planning models aim to find combinations of meals that best fulfil certain objectives. For instance, Seljak (2009) formulate menus for patients with chronic kidney diseases, while Segredo et al. (2020) offer healthy and balanced meal plans for school lunches with minimum cost and maximum variety. Martos-Barrachina et al. (2024) design nutritious menu plans and analyse the trade-off between the cost and palatability of menus, and Benvenuti et al. (2016) aim to formulate meal plans for Italian schools to reduce GHGE and water use.

Akkaş and Gaur (2022) identified mathematical programming as an impactful way to research trade-offs involved in food waste reduction. Van Rooijen et al. (2024) have incorporated discrete package sizes in a meal planning problem to account for food waste. So far diet modelling and meal planning studies have focused on formulating meal plans for a fixed time span. However, real life planning is influenced by everyday unpredictability. Therefore, a flexible mathematical modelling approach is required to study preferable shopping frequencies to minimize food waste.

A rolling horizon approach is a dynamic method for solving sequential decision problems over time (Glomb et al., 2022). Depending on the available information, the decision problem is solved for a certain period of time (forecast horizon), and then shifted forward by a short period of time. The rolling horizon approach has been applied to many optimization problems that are characterized by uncertainty and incomplete information. This includes problems in the fields of humanitarian logistics (Huang et al., 2015), railway disruption management (Nielsen et al., 2012), energy planning (Cuisinier et al., 2022), and production planning (Yang et al., 2005).

In this work, a rolling horizon approach is applied to meal planning to simulate food planning and minimize waste. This method allows the model to adjust as new information becomes available, reflecting how households adapt their meal plans based on changing needs and available ingredients. Meal planning in real life likely resembles a rolling horizon process. Meal planning is an ongoing process with no clear beginning or ending, as there are usually some food items on stock. These leftover food items can subsequently be used for the preparation of future meals, until they expire.

3. Materials and methods

A rolling horizon model is developed to determine how shopping frequencies affect food waste. A rolling horizon is needed to capture the dynamics of food provisioning over time. This model aims to select recipes from a database and formulate dinner meal plans for a varying number of days in advance, while reacting to changes in number of diners and considering leftover ingredients from previous days.

An example of the rolling horizon approach applied to meal planning is shown in Fig. 1. Meals are selected and food shopping is done for a set period (the forecast horizon), which is three days in the example given. The first model step in the example formulates a meal plan for Monday, Tuesday, and Wednesday; shopping is always done on the first day. On the next day, the second model step may reevaluate the

plan for the remaining days of the period, Tuesday and Wednesday. Reevaluations may happen daily but changes only occur in the case of unexpected events. The objective for each period is to have the least amount of perishable food item leftovers. Therefore, combinations of meals are selected based on the complementarity of food package sizes. For example, if one meal requires 150 g of an ingredient and this ingredient is solely available in packages of 400 g, also selecting a meal which requires 250 g of this ingredient might be favourable. Furthermore, the meals selected have to meet the nutritional requirements. After each period (for instance on Thursday in the example), food item stocks are updated, perished foods are put to waste, and the process of meal selection and food shopping is repeated. Every day there is a chance that family members eat elsewhere or that unexpected guests join for dinner. These events may lead to left-overs or may require additional shopping trips. As a guest joined on Saturday in the example, shopping and meal planning was done on Saturday instead of Sunday.

In this research, three distinct family profiles are defined to capture varying levels of dynamics in food planning. Food planning is simulated for these family profiles and for various shopping frequencies to assess the trade-offs between shopping flexibility and advance menu planning on food waste reduction.

It is assumed that recipes are selected and shopping is done on the first day of the forecast horizon. However, when a disruption in the plan occurs and people unexpectedly join for dinner, the forecast horizon is reset, and the process of recipe selection and shopping starts over (as shown in the example on Saturday in Fig. 1), while considering previously purchased stock. Furthermore, finishing food items on stock close to expiration is prioritized. The model focuses on dinner recipes because foods commonly consumed during dinner, such as vegetables, potatoes, and meat, substantially contribute to food waste (Voedingscentrum, 2020). Additionally, dinner foods are typically not consumed at other times of the day in the Netherlands (RIVM, 2022). It is also assumed that people within a household have dinner together.

3.1. Meal planning model

An overview of the meal planning model is shown in Fig. 2.

3.1.1. Objective function

The model aims to minimize household food waste. Any food item remaining in stock at the end of its shelf life is considered waste. Since the shelf life exceeds the forecast horizon of the model, a second term is added to the objective function to minimize perishable food items in stock. Without this term, the model might suggest purchasing excess items, disregarding that they must be consumed before their expiration in future periods. These two terms in the objective function are assigned weights of $w_1 = 0.8$ and $w_2 = 0.2$, respectively, based on preliminary tests that balanced minimizing waste in the current period with avoiding overstocking to prevent waste in the future. The objective function is formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize} \{ & \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{d \in D} w_1 * WASTE_{i,d} + \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{f=1}^F w_2 * STOCK_{i,d=D,f} \\ & + \epsilon_1 * GHGE + \epsilon_2 * COST \} \end{aligned}$$

When alternative optimal solutions exist, tiebreaking terms favour solutions that minimize greenhouse gas emissions (GHGE) and cost (COST). The weights of these terms, denoted by ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 , are $1 * 10^{-7}$ and $5 * 10^{-5}$, respectively. These parameter values are selected such that they do not affect the main objective value, which is waste, but favour solutions with lower GHGE and cost when possible. Moreover, they are chosen such that the weighted contributions of GHGE and cost are of a similar order of magnitude, ensuring they are equally balanced. GHGE are measured in grams of CO₂ equivalents and are calculated using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) data for the ingredients. For both GHGE and cost, the entire package is considered for perishable

Fig. 1. Rolling horizon meal planning approach — example for n days and thus n model steps (i.e. the daily evaluations), with a forecast horizon of 3 days. *Note that somebody joined for dinner on Saturday, therefore the forecast horizon was reset in step 6.

Fig. 2. General overview meal planning model and data.

items, while only the portion actually used is considered for shelf-stable items. Moreover, it is assumed that the largest and cheapest (per kg) package sizes are used for the shelf stable ingredients. GHGE and cost are denoted by the following equations:

$$GHGE = \sum_{i \in S} \sum_{p \in P_i} lca_{c_i} * packs_{i,p} * BUY_{i,p} + \sum_{i \in S} \sum_{d \in D} lca_{c_i} * X_{i,d}$$

$$COST = \sum_{i \in S} \sum_{p \in P_i} packc_{i,p} * BUY_{i,p} + \sum_{i \in S} \sum_{d \in D} (packc_{i,p=\max(P_i)} / packs_{i,p=\max(P_i)}) * X_{i,d}$$

Note that the objective is minimized (only) for the days within the forecast horizon. When this study refers to total waste, GHGE, or costs, it denotes the sum of these respective terms over the entire span of the total horizon.

3.1.2. Constraints

At first, the stock of the day is initialized. Note that f keeps track of the number of days a certain food item has been on stock in the household. Fresh food items can only be bought on the first day of the forecast horizon and are added to the stock by the following constraints:

$$STOCK_{i,d=0,f=1} = \sum_{p \in P_i} pack_{s_{i,p}} * BUY_{i,p} \quad \forall i \in I \quad (1)$$

Furthermore, food items of the previous day which are not yet expired are added to the stock:

$$STOCK_{i,d=0,f} = beginstock_{i,f} \quad \forall i \in I, \forall f \in F > 1 \quad (2)$$

Ingredients which are not used before their expiry date are wasted:

$$WASTE_{i,d} = STOCK_{i,d,f=\max(F)} \quad \forall i \in I, \forall d \in D \quad (3)$$

Two types of balance constraints are formulated; constraints to balance total stock levels, and constraints to balance stock levels for each f .

Constraints (4) balance total stock levels. For each day, stock levels equal the stock levels of the previous day minus ingredients used $X_{i,d}$ and ingredients wasted $WASTE_{i,d}$.

$$\sum_{f=1}^F STOCK_{i,d,f} = \sum_{f=1}^F STOCK_{i,d-1,f} - WASTE_{i,d-1} - X_{i,d} \quad \forall d \in D, \forall i \in I \quad (4)$$

Constraints (5) and (6) balance stock levels for each f . They ensure that food items on stock mature each day d . Furthermore, they ensure that food items used on day d are subtracted from stock following the “first in, first out” principle. If a certain $STOCK_{i,d,f}$ cannot fulfil $X_{i,d}$, the stock is set to 0 to ensure non-negativity. As day 0 merely acts as an initialization phase, stock does not mature from day 0 to day 1, as seen in Constraints (5).

$$STOCK_{d=1,f} = \max\{0, STOCK_{d=0,f} - X_{i,d} + \sum_{v=f+1}^F STOCK_{d=0,v} - \sum_{v=f+1}^F STOCK_{1,v}\} \quad \forall d \in D, \forall i \in I, \forall f \in F \quad (5)$$

$$STOCK_{d,f} = \max\{0, STOCK_{d-1,f-1} - X_{i,d} + \sum_{v=f}^{F-1} STOCK_{d-1,v} - \sum_{v=f+1}^F STOCK_{d,v}\} \quad \forall d \in D, \forall i \in I, \forall f \in F \quad (6)$$

Constraints (7) ensure that one recipe r is planned per day, while Constraints (8) prevent recipes r from being repeated within the total horizon:

$$\sum_{r \in R} Y_{r,d} = 1 \quad \forall d \in D \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{r \in R} Y_{r,d} + eaten_r \leq 1 \quad \forall d \in D \quad (8)$$

The requirements for ingredient i on day d are calculated based on the recipe:

$$REQ_{i,d} = pers * \sum_{r \in R} ingr_{i,r} * Y_{r,d} \quad \forall i \in I, \forall d \in D \quad (9)$$

Constraints (10) ensure that the binary variable $Z_{i,d}$ is 1 if ingredient i is scheduled on day d according to the recipe, and 0 otherwise. Constraints (11) and (12) allow the quantity of ingredient i planned on day d to deviate by up to 10 g from the amount specified in the recipe for that day.

$$REQ_{i,d} \geq 0.01 * Z_{i,d} \quad \forall i \in I, \forall d \in D \quad (10)$$

$$X_{i,d} \leq REQ_{i,d} + 10 * Z_{i,d} \quad \forall i \in I, \forall d \in D \quad (11)$$

$$X_{i,d} \geq REQ_{i,d} - 10 * Z_{i,d} \quad \forall i \in I, \forall d \in D \quad (12)$$

The total nutrient contents of the meal plan are computed:

$$NI_{j,d} = \sum_{i \in I} (fcd_{i,j}/100) * X_{i,d} \quad \forall j \in J, \forall d \in D \quad (13)$$

Nutrient intakes for each water-soluble nutrient j on each day d must exceed the Recommended Dietary Allowance (RDA) but remain below the Upper Limit (UL) of the dietary reference values set for dinner:

$$NI_{j,d} \geq drvRDA_j * pers \quad \forall j \in JD, \forall d \in D \quad (14)$$

$$NI_{j,d} \leq drvUL_j * pers \quad \forall j \in JD, \forall d \in D \quad (15)$$

As fat soluble nutrients can be stored in the body, they do not have to be consumed in the same quantities every single day. Therefore, the total intakes of fat soluble nutrients j have to meet the dietary reference values across the forecast horizon. Note these constraints are only enforced on the first model run of each forecast horizon:

$$\sum_{d \in D} NI_{j,d} \geq drvRDA_j * pers * days \quad \forall j \in JW \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_{d \in D} NI_{j,d} \leq drvUL_j * pers * days \quad \forall j \in JW \quad (17)$$

3.2. Data and model input

An overview of model inputs is shown in Fig. 2. The model uses fixed input data, such as recipes, while updating other parameters, such as food stocks, based on the results of previous iterations.

A set of 403 dinner recipes was obtained from the Netherlands Nutrition Centre (Voedingscentrum, 2023). The recipes selected are full dinners, so no meal components, and conform to the daily nutrient requirements. This study aims to reduce edible food waste. Therefore, food quantities were converted to edible weights (e.g. a banana without its peel) using the Dutch portion sizes database (RIVM, 2020). The Dutch Food Composition Database (FCD) which contains the nutrient contents of the most common Dutch foods was retrieved from the RIVM (RIVM, 2021b). The most common household in the Netherlands includes a man, a woman, and two children (CBS, 2023a). This household structure, with a moderately active lifestyle, is taken as the focal point of the study. Dietary Reference Values (DRVs) for dinner in the Netherlands were based on the dietary guidelines of the Dutch Health Council and derived for this most common household (Gezondheidsraad, 2022, 2018). Moreover, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) data was obtained from the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) and used to quantify the environmental impact of the meals planned (RIVM, 2021a). Food package and price data have been obtained from a large Dutch retailer. For each food item, the net weight, package size in grams and package price was collected on June 27, 2024.

Shelf life is defined as the time between production and the expiry date (Buisman et al., 2019). In the supermarket there are perishable products with a “best-by” expiry date (e.g. yoghurt), “use-by” expiry date (e.g. chicken), or without an explicit expiry date (e.g. apples). Determining which shelf lives to use as model input is rather challenging for multiple reasons. First, the number of days to expiry of a certain product on the shelf in the supermarket is not constant, normally supermarkets employ a “first-in first-out” strategy when filling the shelves. Second, fresh fruit and vegetables have no expiration dates, and their expiry is strongly dependent on the quality of the product. Third, the expiry dates of food products are based on the conditions of the unopened food package. This research distinguishes between shelf-stable and perishable food items based on data from the Netherlands Nutrition Center (Voedingscentrum, 2023). In this dataset, the shelf life of perishable food items is typically given as a range and depends heavily on whether the product has been opened or cut (in the case of vegetables and fruits). The model used in this study only suggests purchasing food items that will be used within the next few days. The median shelf life of food items opened one day after purchase is four days. Therefore, a shelf life of four days is assumed for all perishable food items in the model.

Table 1
Base case configuration.

Parameter	Value
Total horizon	21 days
Forecast horizon	1, 2, 3, or 4 days
Shelf life	4 days
Household size	4 persons
Family profile	1; predictable 2; occasional changes 3; dynamic

Three distinct family profiles are introduced to capture varying levels of predictability in household food planning. Family profile 1 represents households with a predictable and stable lifestyle, where no changes occur in the number of persons dining at home. Family profile 2 represents households that experience occasional changes in dining plans. Once or twice a week an additional person joins for dinner or a household member dines elsewhere. Family profile 3 represents households with a dynamic routine. Three or four times a week an additional person joins for dinner or a household member might dine elsewhere. It is assumed that the number of persons dining at home is certain only on the current day. For instance, while it is uncertain on Monday how many people will dine at home on Wednesday, the exact number will be known on Wednesday itself.

3.3. Base case configuration

The base case scenario configuration is shown in Table 1. The total horizon is set to 21 days, which is assumed to be long enough to simulate food shopping and planning patterns and reduce the end-of-horizon effects, yet short enough to limit model complexity and avoid the need of additional recipe repetition assumptions. Recipe repetition is not allowed within the total horizon. The formulated meal plans are reevaluated daily. The forecast horizon, which determines shopping frequency, is set to either one, two, three, or four days. Perishable products are assumed to have a shelf life of four days. The household in the base scenario consists of four persons. This household's planning uncertainty is varied and is categorized as family profile 1 for predictable schedules, family profile 2 for occasional plan changes, or family profile 3 for a dynamic lifestyle.

3.4. Computational setup

The model has been solved using the Gurobi package in Python 3.6. Each step within the rolling horizon model is restricted to a run time limit of 800 s, due to the absence of further improvements of the objective value after this time. Note that a full run of the rolling horizon model comprises 21 steps. Each combination of a forecast horizon and family profile is referred to as a distinct scenario. The rolling horizon model is solved 30 times for the scenarios including family profile 2 or 3, to simulate the effects of the inherent uncertainty in family profiles where the number of diners might vary. The Interquartile Range (IQR) method is applied to remove outliers, where data points below $Q1 - 1.5 * IQR$ or above $Q3 + 1.5 * IQR$ are considered outliers.

4. Results

For the base case, a simulation was run thirty times for each distinct combination of family profile and forecast horizon. A full overview of the simulation runs, an example of the model output, and a demonstration of the calculation of waste can be found in the Supplementary Data. The average food waste after removing outliers is shown in Fig. 3. Generally, increased uncertainty in food planning leads to greater food waste, regardless of the shopping frequency. For family profile 1, food waste only occurs with a forecast horizon of one day (53 g) because planning just one day in advance prevents efficient alignment with food

package sizes. No waste occurs with forecast horizons of two, three, or four days. Whereas a lower shopping frequency (longer forecast horizon) leads to less food waste for family profile 1, this does not apply to family profiles 2 and 3. For family profile 2, the least amount of food waste occurs with a two-day forecast horizon. For family profile 3, a one-day forecast horizon is optimal.

Another simulation was conducted in which the household size varied from one to five persons, to simulate the effect of household size on food planning (Fig. 4). The pattern of optimal shopping frequencies remains similar across different household sizes. However, smaller households incur more food waste, especially when uncertainty increases. This can partly be explained by the way in which uncertainty is modelled in this research, where disruptions have a relatively greater effect on small households. Additionally, it is more challenging for smaller households to finish perishable products on time due to the fixed portions of foods, such as cauliflowers or packed salads.

In addition to household size, shelf life was varied in the simulations. The number of days an opened or unopened food product is edible is not strictly determined by food safety guidelines, except for 'use-by' products. Instead, for these 'best before' products consumers are advised to rely on their senses to decide if a product remains edible (Zeinstra et al., 2021). Besides factors such as product type, product quality, and storage conditions, consumer preferences determine when a product is discarded. While some consumers prefer to consume only the freshest products, others are more flexible regarding a product's edibility (Gunden and Thomas, 2012). To explore this variability, an analysis was conducted by extending the shelf life of food products from four to five days (Fig. 5). For family profile 1, food waste remains similar to that of the four-day shelf life across all forecast horizons, and for family profile 2 with one or two-day horizons. However, extending the shelf life to five days leads to substantial reductions in food waste in cases of increased uncertainty and longer forecast horizons. For instance, for family profile 3 with a three-day forecast horizon, average food waste decreases from 299 g to 133 g. Overall, food waste patterns are similar for both shelf lives, except that the scenario with the lowest food waste for family profile 2 shifted from a two-day to a three-day forecast horizon.

To evaluate the relationship between the forecast horizon and the type of recipes selected, the number of fish-based, meat-based, and vegetarian meals selected by the model are assessed (Fig. 6). For each scenario thirty meal plans, each spanning 21 days, are simulated. For example, in the scenario for family profile 2 with a two-day forecast horizon, this results in a total of 630 recipes (21 days * 30 plans). The analysis shows that vegetarian recipes are selected most frequently across all scenarios. However, for shorter forecast horizons, fewer vegetarian recipes are chosen. This is because shorter forecast horizons favour smaller package sizes due to the model's preference for minimizing perishable food stocks at the end of each forecast horizon. Unlike many meat and fish products, which are often packaged in single-use portions, vegetables are packaged in larger portions. As a result, not all vegetables are fully used in each recipe, making them less attractive for shorter forecast horizons.

The objective of the model is to minimize food waste. When alternative meal plans result in equal food waste, those with lower GHGE and costs are preferred. The average GHGE and cost for the simulated meal plans in each case are presented in Table 2. Notably, for all family profiles, both GHGE and cost decrease as the forecast horizon increases. This trend resembles the decrease in fish and meat-based recipes selected as shown in Fig. 6. As mentioned earlier, shorter forecast horizons favour the use of fish and meat due to their convenient package sizes. Since fish and meat tend to have high GHGE and costs, this explains the higher costs and emissions associated with shorter forecast horizons. Additionally, for most food products larger package sizes are more cost-effective, which can create a trade-off between reducing food waste and minimizing costs. Therefore, the meal plans

Fig. 3. Average food waste per family profile and forecast horizon (4 persons, 21 days, shelf life 4 days). Family profile 1 is predictable, family profile 2 occasionally changes plans, and family profile 3 leads a dynamic lifestyle.

Fig. 4. Average food waste per household size, family profile, and forecast horizon (21 days, shelf life 4 days). Note that waste is depicted per household and not per person.

Fig. 5. Average food waste per family profile and forecast horizon (4 persons, 21 days, shelf life 5 days).

with minimum waste do not necessarily have the lowest GHGE and cost.

5. Discussion

This study identifies a trade-off between being maintaining adaptability and coordinating food purchases, contributing to the ongoing

debate in literature regarding shopping strategies to reduce food waste. Prior research shows that planning practices can substantially reduce food waste (Ananda et al., 2023; Stefan et al., 2013; Van Rooijen et al., 2024; Giordano et al., 2019). However, other research emphasizes that the dynamic and unpredictable nature of every day life makes it difficult to engage in such planning (Dobernic and Schanes, 2019;

Fig. 6. Number of meat-based, fish-based, and vegetarian meals selected per family profile and forecast horizon (4 persons, 21 days, shelf life 4 days).

Table 2

Average waste, greenhouse gas emissions, and costs for each family profile and forecast horizon (FH) (4 persons, 21 days, shelf life 4 days). While the primary objective was to minimize waste, greenhouse gas emissions and costs were also considered as part of the analysis.

Family	FH (days)	Waste (grams)	GHGE (grams CO ₂ eq)	Cost (€)
family1	1	53	185,269	325
family1	2	0	167,962	308
family1	3	0	83,960	198
family1	4	0	88,866	226
family2	1	52	179,005	319
family2	2	30	134,233	266
family2	3	81	100,252	225
family2	4	409	94,095	224
family3	1	46	172,256	309
family3	2	127	130,400	260
family3	3	292	111,781	229
family3	4	969	103,795	232

Evans, 2015; Ganglbauer et al., 2013). Therefore, Ellison et al. (2022) advocate letting go of planning and shopping more frequently to reduce uncertainty in food requirements. Since shopping frequency is a measurable behaviour that influences meal planning, it is an effective variable for studying waste reduction strategies. The theoretical interrelations of shopping frequency, uncertainty, and food waste as found in this study provide a foundation for designing interventions targeted to reduce food waste (Reynolds et al., 2019; Stancu et al., 2016).

The results suggest that the optimal shopping frequency depends on the level of uncertainty a household faces. The results of this study suggest that households with a predictable lifestyle should shop less frequently than households with a dynamic lifestyle to reduce food waste. Previous research on food waste reduction interventions highlights that segmenting households helps develop better-targeted interventions (Swannell et al., 2023). Consequently, instead of suggesting a one-size-fits-all approach regarding shopping frequency, this study proposes that food waste reduction approaches should differentiate based on the level of uncertainty households face. Interventions could target predictable households with guidance on meal planning, while

encouraging adaptive shopping strategies for households facing greater uncertainty.

The simulation results indicate that the average food waste over a 21 day period is negligible for the optimal forecast horizons for each family profile (Fig. 3). This implies that by accounting for uncertainty and focusing on finishing current stock levels, food purchasing strategies can be found that result in low food waste levels. Previous research confirms that selecting recipes and buying foods based on what is missing at home is one of the most important skills to reduce food waste (Veselá et al., 2023; Woolley et al., 2022). The findings suggest that interventions aimed at improving household awareness of stock levels could effectively reduce food waste.

The model considers discrete package sizes as available in retail, which complicate meal planning, especially for shorter forecast horizons and smaller households. In shorter forecast horizons, there is less flexibility to allocate certain foods across meals, leading to increased waste from mismatched portions. In such cases, fish- and meat-based recipes are selected relatively often because fish and meat are typically portioned in single-use packages, whereas certain vegetables, such as lettuce, are not always used up at once. Additionally, it is more challenging for smaller households to finish perishable products on time due to fixed package sizes, resulting in significantly more food waste per person in the simulations for smaller households than for larger households. Previous studies report similar results based on food consumption surveys and household food waste data (Smith and Landry, 2021; Silvennoinen et al., 2014). This finding indicates that offering more flexible portion sizes could reduce food waste.

The objective of this model was to reduce food waste. However, reducing food waste comes with trade-offs related to GHGE and costs. For example, larger package sizes are more cost-effective but less suitable for reducing waste, while meat and fish often come in convenient package sizes but contribute to higher GHGE. As a result, the meal plans proposed to minimize waste do not necessarily have the lowest GHGE and cost. Nevertheless, these minimum waste meal plans still lead to a reduction of GHGE by 3% to 30% compared to the average GHGE of a Dutch dinner for the target family (Vellinga et al., 2019).

This study explores the effect of uncertainty in meal planning by introducing three distinct family profiles, which differ in the (fixed)

probabilities that guests join for dinner or family members dine elsewhere. In the model, disruptions involve a change of exactly one person in the number of people present for a meal, making smaller households more heavily affected. Future research could develop more complex family profiles that account for variable and context specific disruptions to fully capture the diversity of household behaviours and preferences. Another limitation in the model is the assumption about shelf life. A fixed shelf life of four days from purchase is assumed for perishable products, based on data on the expiration of opened products. However, shelf life also depends on factors such as product quality and storage conditions, which were beyond the scope of this study. As a result, the analysis focuses on the relationship between shopping frequency and food waste rather than the absolute results. An extended shelf life analysis indicates that this can substantially reduce food waste. Future research could further explore the relation between a flexible attitude to shelf life and food waste. Moreover, another model assumption is the use of fixed weights to balance food waste and perishable stock. Future research could explore how decisions regarding perishable stock in the current period influence food waste across longer planning horizons.

While the theoretical insights from this study highlight promising food planning and shopping strategies, there are behavioural factors that could limit their practical impact. For instance, multiple studies have shown that consumers are often tempted to buy more food items than needed when going to the supermarket, due to factors such as discount offers, supermarket design, or going shopping hungry (Hultén and Vanyushyn, 2011). However, Stefan et al. (2013) suggest that making shopping lists reduces the risk of buying unnecessary produce.

Additionally, consumer preferences regarding shopping frequency might play a role. Ellison et al. (2022) indicate that consumers are more averse to extra shopping trips than to food waste, primarily due to the time and travel costs associated with shopping. If the distance to a supermarket is large, the environmental impact of an extra shopping trip might even offset environmental gains from reducing food waste. Although this study focuses on the Netherlands, where the average distance to a supermarket is rather short (0.9 km) (CBSb, 2023), future research could explore how incorporating the GHGE from supermarket trips influences optimal shopping frequencies.

Although the Netherlands is taken as case study, the general insights gathered from this study are expected to be applicable in other contexts. However, there are some important considerations when applying the model to different parts of the world. First, as mentioned before, the distance to supermarkets may influence the feasibility of frequent shopping. Furthermore, in the Netherlands foods that are consumed at dinner are usually not consumed throughout the rest of the day. In countries where this is not the case, incorporating other meal moments beyond dinner could improve the model's accuracy. Finally, the variety of package sizes might differ across regions. In countries where fresh produce is more commonly consumed, more frequent shopping trips may be necessary compared to countries where a larger proportion of food is sold in bulk.

6. Conclusions

This work aims to isolate the effects of shopping frequency and uncertainty in food requirements on household food waste using a rolling horizon modelling approach. The results show that there is a trade-off between the flexibility of frequent shopping and the benefits of coordinated food purchasing. Households with a predictable lifestyle benefit from lower shopping frequencies than households that face greater uncertainty. Additionally, the analysis shows that selecting recipes and shopping based on available food items in the household can reduce food waste. It is therefore advocated that interventions targeting household food waste tailor advice regarding shopping frequencies based on the level of uncertainty households face, and to provide households with tools to select recipes and buy food based on what is missing at home. While minimizing food waste was the

primary objective of this study, the findings also reveal trade-offs with greenhouse gas emissions and costs, mainly due to the convenient package sizing of meat and fish products.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

M.A. van Rooijen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **J.C. Gerdessen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **G.D.H. Claassen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **S.L.J.M. de Leeuw:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2025.05.015>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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